

The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded in Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr phase so as to locate mainly the Cr=O stretching band. The frequencies for this band, which center round 940-955 cm^{-1} are in accordance with the previous observations⁷ in similar cases.

The esr spectra of the powdered compounds were recorded on Varian V-4502 ESR spectrophotometer using X-band (9.3 GHz) r. f. field and the average $\langle g \rangle$ values were calculated. These were found to be in accordance with the low symmetry distorted octahedral field⁸ caused by the interaction of strong Cr-O multiple bond and are supported by oxidation states and values of magnetic moments. The values of molar conductance, magnetic moments, frequencies of Cr=O stretching bands and the average $\langle g \rangle$ values are given in Table 2.

The electronic spectra of the compounds were taken on Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer in acetonitrile and the bands along with the assignments on the basis of previous reports⁹⁻¹⁰ on similar compounds are given in Table 3.

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Thermodynamic Parameters of Dialkyltin(IV)-N-Arylhydroxamic Acid Chelates

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ALTHOUGH the chemistry of dialkyltin(IV) in non-aqueous media has received wide attention, information about the stability of the complexes in solution is rather meagre^{1,2}. The present work describes for the first time the thermodynamic

functions of some chelates formed by N-arylhydroxamic acids (N-phenylbenzhydroxamic, N-p-tolylbenzhydroxamic acids) with dialkyltin(IV) ions [dimethyl-, di-n-propyl- and di-n-butyltin(IV) dichlorides]. The stability constants were computed in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 20, 30 and 40° by Calvin-Bjerrum technique^{3,4} as adapted by Rossotti and Irving⁵ employing different computational methods viz., \bar{n} and pL plot, correction term and least square methods. Thermodynamic quantities, ΔG , ΔH , ΔS and ΔCp , were calculated for the following equilibrium using the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ data.

(R' = C₆H₅, p-C₆H₄CH₃; R = CH₃, n-C₂H₇ and n-C₄H₉)

Experimental

Dialkyltin(IV) dichlorides were distilled before use. Dioxane was dried and purified by standard methods. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiments. The chelating agents, N-arylhydroxamic acids, were synthesized by the reported methods^{6,7}. For the determination of dissociation constants^{8,9}, a solution of 0.01 M hydroxamic acid and 0.1 M NaCl in 75% dioxane-water (v/v) was titrated against 0.5 M NaOH solution at 20, 30 and 40°. Potentiometric studies were carried out on a digital pH meter (model pH 5651) of ECIL, India. All measurements were taken in nitrogen atmosphere with constant stirring magnetically. Since complexation⁸ of Cl⁻ with dialkyltin(IV) ion is negligible, metal chlorides were used for obtaining formation constant data. To avoid hydrolysis of dialkyltin ions, the present studies were carried out in dioxane-water media^{6,7}.

A solution containing 0.01 M hydroxamic acid, 0.0025 M dialkyltin(IV) dichloride and 0.1 M NaCl was titrated against 0.1 M NaOH for obtaining formation constants. Correction factors¹⁰ ($\log \mu H = 0.08$ at 20°, 0.13 at 30° and 0.17 at 40°) were applied to the observed pH values to obtain the correct pH in dioxane-water media. The average number of the ligand bound per metal ion (\bar{n}) and the free ligand concentration (L) were calculated by the literature procedure^{6,7}. The stepwise formation constants $\log q_1$ and $\log q_2$ were directly read from n, pL plot and were also computed by the least square and the correction term methods. The first, second and overall formation constants determined during the present investigation are given in Table 1. The change in free energy ($-\Delta G$) was calculated from the equation $-\Delta G = 2.303 RT \log \beta$, where R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature and $\log \beta$ = overall stability constant. The other thermodynamic functions (ΔH , ΔS and ΔCp) were calculated by plotting¹¹ the $\log \beta$ (stoichiometric or thermodynamic stability constant) vs T^{-1} . ΔH was calculated from the slope and ΔS from the intercept data.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FORMATION CONSTANTS OF DIALKYL TIN(IV)-HYDROXAMIC ACID SYSTEMS (LEAST SQUARE METHOD)

Hydroxamic acid (C ₆ H ₅ CONR'OH) R'	Temp. °C	Formation constants			Thermodynamic formation constants		
		log q ₁	log q ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
Chelates of dimethyltin(IV) dichloride							
C ₆ H ₅	20	8.93	7.31	16.24	12.49	9.09	21.58
	30	8.91	7.26	16.17	12.66	9.14	21.80
	40	9.02	7.24	16.26	12.82	9.14	21.96
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	20	9.26	7.49	16.75	12.82	9.27	22.09
	30	9.20	7.41	16.61	12.88	9.25	22.13
	40	9.14	7.32	16.46	12.96	9.22	22.16
Chelates of di- <i>n</i> -propyltin dichloride							
C ₆ H ₅	20	9.22	6.52	15.74	12.78	8.30	21.08
	30	9.20	6.54	15.74	12.88	8.38	21.26
	40	9.23	6.51	15.74	13.03	8.41	21.44
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	20	9.61	7.49	17.10	13.17	9.27	22.44
	30	9.42	7.57	16.99	13.10	9.41	22.51
	40	9.34	7.59	16.93	13.14	9.49	22.63
Chelates of di- <i>n</i> -butyltin dichloride							
C ₆ H ₅	20	9.28	6.42	15.70	12.84	8.20	21.04
	30	9.29	6.65	15.95	12.97	8.49	21.46
	40	9.18	6.95	16.13	12.98	8.85	21.83
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	20	9.58	7.54	17.12	13.14	9.32	22.46
	30	9.55	7.42	16.97	13.23	9.26	22.49
	40	9.39	7.50	16.89	13.19	9.40	22.59

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Hydroxamic acid (C ₆ H ₅ CONR'OH) R'	Metal ion	-ΔG(k. cal/mole)			ΔH (k.cal/mole)	ΔS cal/mole
		-ΔG ₁₀₀	-ΔG ₂₀₀	-ΔG ₃₀₀		
C ₆ H ₅	(CH ₃) ₂ SnCl ₂	28.93	30.22	31.45	0.00823	42.89
	(<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉) ₂ SnCl ₂	28.26	29.47	30.70	0.00846	41.88
	(<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃) ₂ SnCl ₂	28.21	29.74	31.26	0.01807	41.80
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ SnCl ₂	29.61	30.68	31.73	0.00183	43.89
	(<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉) ₂ SnCl ₂	30.08	31.21	32.41	0.00257	44.58
	(<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃) ₂ SnCl ₂	30.11	31.18	32.35	0.00297	44.62

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometric formation constants have been calculated from the interpolation and half \bar{n} values, correction term and least square methods. Since the results from the above three methods were in good agreement, only the least square method was employed for the thermodynamic parameter calculations. Thermodynamic formation constants were calculated by adding the correction term of the glass electrode in the corresponding values of log q₁ and log q₂. The first, second and overall formation constants determined are given in Table 1. The first formation constant of dialkyltin(IV)-hydroxamic acid systems increases with the change of alkyl group from methyl to butyl in R₂Sn(IV), possibly due to the increase in the electrophilic character of tin with the increase in the length of the alkyl chain¹². The overall formation constants, log β, have been calculated by log K₁K₂ values. The values of log β at different temperatures increase for the same organotin(IV) ion and decrease at the same temperature for different organotin(IV) ions. This implies that for a organotin(IV) ion at different temperatures (in the increasing way) the formation of the complex is spontaneous process¹³ and the

degree of formation of the complex decreases as the alkyl group becomes bulkier.

Thermodynamic complexation: The ΔG values (Table 2) for a particular diorganotin(IV) ion and at a particular temperature increases from N-phenyl to N-*p*-tolylbenzhydroxamic acid. A similar trend is observed for a set of diorganotin-hydroxamic acid with increase of temperature. The heats of association have been derived¹⁴ by the use of least square from the linear plots of log β against T⁻¹ as shown in Fig. 1. The plotting of log β vs T⁻¹ should result in a straight line¹¹ with a slope of $-\frac{\Delta H}{R}$ and an intercept of $\frac{\Delta S}{R}$ where R is the gas constant. The values of ΔH and ΔS calculated from the slope and intercepts of the lines are given in Table 2.

Comparing the relative values of the thermodynamic quantities, the data (Table 2) show that as expected, there is a substantial change in the enthalpy of the complexes as the alkyl group on the tin or the ligand becomes bulkier. Entropy has been calculated for both the systems and for all the different diorganotin(IV) ions by the relation

$\Delta S = \text{intercept} \times R$ (Table 2). The observed positive values of ΔS indicate the spontaneous formation of the complexes^{1,3}. The plots of $\log \beta$ against T^{-1} (Fig. 1) are straight lines which indicate that the values of ΔC_p are equal to zero^{1,6}.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log \beta$ against T^{-1} for

- (1) $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
- (2) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
- (3) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
- (4) $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$
- (5) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$
- (6) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$

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Solution Stabilities of Some Biligand Chelates of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II) with 1,10-Phenanthroline and Substituted Salicylic Acids

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LIKE 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline also forms stable complexes with metal ions at low pH which remain stable even at higher pH. Both have, therefore, been used widely as primary ligand in the study of a variety of mixed ligand complexes¹⁻⁷. Ternary complexes of the secondary ligands used in the present studies with a number of metal ions, using 2,2'-bipyridine as the primary ligand, have been reported^{6,7}. We report here the results of studies on mixed ligand chelates of copper(II), nickel(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) with 1,10-phenanthroline (primary ligand) and 4-hydroxy, 4-methyl and 3-methyl salicylic acids (secondary ligands) by pH metric method using a modified Irving and Rossotti technique⁸. Measurements were made at 25°, $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaNO_3) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol.

The formation constants of the binary complexes of the secondary ligands have also been determined under similar conditions for a comparative study of both the types of the systems.

Experimental

Solutions of metal nitrates, sodium hydroxide, sodium nitrate and nitric acid were prepared in double distilled water and used after standardisation^{9,10}. Solutions of the ligands, phen, 4-HSA, 4-MSA and 3-MSA were prepared in redistilled ethanol by direct weighing. All chemicals were of analytical grade.

Measurements of pH were made with an expanded scale Elico pH meter (Model LI-15) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly at 25°. pH-Metric titrations were performed as described earlier^{6,7}. The final concentrations were $N^0 = 0.1 M$, $E^0 = 0.002 M$, $TC_L^0 = TC_M^0 = TC_{phen}^0 = 0.001 M$. All symbols have their usual meanings¹⁰. Figures of the titration curves are not shown here. The formation constants corresponding to proton ligand, binary M-L and ternary M-phen-L complexing systems were calculated as described earlier^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

The protonation constants of the secondary ligands are presented in Table I. Formation curves of proton-secondary ligand systems are not shown here as they were given earlier^{6,7}. The basicity

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